

A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF CUSTOMER SATISFACTION IN PRIVATE AND PUBLIC SECTOR BANKS

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ABSTRACT

The country's banking sector should be seen as an amazing economic offerings business, since it is mostly responsible for the overall financial improvement of the nation. Customer satisfaction is important from an operational standpoint since it helps retain present customers and draw in new ones. In India, financial services are currently provided by both the public and private sectors. Due to the different marketing approaches and appeals of private and public banks, there has been a shift in the perception of patron pride to varying degrees. As a result, this study aims to establish customer satisfaction at India's public and private banks and investigates the factors that influence customer satisfaction on various levels. Learn about goals in order to choose the degree of pleasure, and whether or not the difference in pride could also be a part of changeable factors or an absence of a comparable that can lead to unhappiness or discontent in public or private banks. The primary data used for this search was obtained from Indian banks operating in the public and private leisure domains. Because of the high worker performance, public area banks like Citibank were able to operate quite well and guarantee customer pleasure. To improve the job satisfaction of staff members whose public banks use tangible equipment and behavioural factors, long-term interventions are needed.

Keywords: Customer Satisfaction, Services Quality, ATMs, Technology

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INTRODUCTION

As a result, this topic, which focuses on connections and interpreting the client's pleasure, plays a crucial role in increasing the standard profitability and financial profitability of all service-related businesses. The banking industry is the only industry that deals with financial services. The customer's satisfaction has an even greater impact on a bank-focused company's ability to stay in business. Consumers are happy; nevertheless, the level of service at each banking provider stage depends on the type and comfort of the benefits the provider offers. There are a variety of reasons for financial institutions to differentiate their offers for certain client classes and to charge varying rates of interest. Indian banks, both governmental and private, offer a variety of financial services to both urban and rural customer's areas. The claim that private banks employ five times as many people as state banks is true. Private sector banks' compound annual growth rates are expanding at a rate that is twice as fast as that of public sector banks. The overall and relative growth of public and private area banks is intended to boost customer confidence as they work to draw in new business and retain existing ones. Private zone banks: The main priorities should be lending and insurance policies. Public banks: The client provider continues to be the weak link. Public zone banks should upgrade their physical locations, and the employees who interact with customers there should receive training. Structured variables in banks variables set by the bank Customers want to satisfy their desires Lender is an establishment that satisfies this need. Utilise the newest technological branch. Robust infrastructure and skilled department staff extended business hours and branches in my vicinity.

LITERATURE OF REVIEW

1. SL Gupta and Arun Mittal are the authors of the paper "Comparative research of promotional studies adopted by public sector and private sector banks in India." *Journal of Asia-Pacific Business*, July–September 2008. According to surveys, the public sector is, if not very well, more reliable than the private one. Although a private sector bank may be advantageous when it comes to providing services that are both creative and of high quality, its performance is not nearly as efficient as that of a public sector bank in terms of quality or innovation.
2. Bhallabh (2002) discusses the effects of the reforms to the banking sector: "In an integrated financial market, globalisation and technological advancements have brought about a transformation of the Indian banking system." The state of the market should be taken into account before choosing which policies to execute and how.
3. Kumar (2006) since class orientation was changed to one that accommodated the nation's impoverished peoples' financial exclusion cause, bank nationalisation introduced popular banking to India. Within the framework of international thinking, the emergence of a new obligation and commercialization—which can generate revenue by treating low-income populations as clients and satisfying their needs—were held equally responsible.
4. The Indian banking sector has seen a change from local to international banking, as noted by Subbarao in 2007. Thus, a mixture of contemporary technologies, controlled assessment, treasury management, product mix, and internal controls are required. The international community, for instance, can be that effective tool or process in overcoming the obstacle.
5. As stated by single, "It is the concern with the analysis of profitability position towards over six years period, 16 banks from the banker's index," demonstrating the importance of financial management in the technological rise of banking. A lot of work has gone into this analysis to demonstrate the banks' profitability position. Considerably more reasonable than it was the year before during the trial.

When the balance sheet displays the robust capital base. Banks are useful in mitigating the effects of economic shocks. They haven't changed all that much over time.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To determine which area of banking is most favoured by clients.
2. To ascertain the elements that motivate clients to choose a particular bank.
3. Researching and contrasting the challenges faced by clients of banks in the public and private sectors.
4. A comparison of how banks in the public and private sectors use technology, including ATMs, Internet, phone, and mobile banking.
5. Because Vapi, the sample element, is a semi-urban area with a low concentration of private sector banks, the outcome is probably going to favour public sector banks.

HYPOTHESIS

H0: When it comes to the gender of customer satisfaction, public and private banks do not significantly differ from one another.

H1: When it comes to client satisfaction, public and private banks differ significantly.

H0: The gender of a consumer makes no difference between public and private banks.

H1: There are gender differences between customers of public and commercial banks.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

- **Research design:** The study employs a hybrid methodology, drawing on qualitative research as a foundation while testing the hypothesis using quantitative data.
- **A data source:** Since the information was gathered directly through questionnaires, the data used in this study came from primary data sources. Secondary data is gathered from a variety of websites and earlier academic publications.
- **Data Collection Method:** Surveys were employed in this study to gather data. A survey is a tool used to collect data from a sample of individuals by asking relevant questions in an effort to understand the population as a whole.
- **Population:** The total group about which you wish to make inferences is referred to as the population. The study's conclusions are intended to shed light on Indians' perceptions of how tourism affects culture.
- **Sampling Techniques:** This study employed convenience and random sampling techniques.
- **Sampling Frame:** A sampling frame is any list, document, or other item that specifies, identifies, and permits access to the survey population's constituent parts. It can be used as a foundation for sampling in order to calculate the probability of selection.
- **Data gathering Instrument:** A questionnaire designed for the survey was utilised as the data gathering tool in this investigation.

SAMPLE SIZE

It speaks about how many fundamentals of the population are sampled. A sample size of 130 participants has been chosen for the survey. Research Instrument: Questionnaire; Research Design: Descriptive 130 persons make up the sample. Random sampling is the sampling technique. The graphical method is the analytical tool.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

1. In which Banking sector do you have your account?

<i>Particulars</i>	<i>No of Respondents</i>	<i>Percentage%</i>
Public Sector	60	46.15%
Private Sector	50	38.46%
Both	20	15.38%
Total	130	100%

INTERPRETATION: Based on the aforementioned results, I have determined that, of the 130 respondents, 50 had accounts with private sector banks, 60 with public sector banks, and 20 with both bank sectors.

2. Which types of account you are using in the public sector as well as private sector.

Particulars	No of Respondents	Percentage%
Debit Card	50	38.46%
Credit Card	30	23.07%
Insurance	27	23.07%
Mobile Banking	23	20.76%
Total	130	100%

INTERPRETATION: Based on the aforementioned data, I have determined that, of the 130.100 respondents, 14 have a current account, 10 have a fixed deposit account, and 06 have a demat account with their preferred banks.

3. Which facilities are you availing at your bank?

INTERPRETATION: Based on the aforementioned outcome, I have discovered that 130 responders. More than sixty-two respondents use their bank's debit card services; twenty-nine respondents use mobile banking; twenty-three respondents use insurance; and six respondents use credit cards.

4. What kind of problems are you facing regarding the services provided by their preferred bank?

Particulars	Percentage%
Reference	29%
Time Consuming	33%
Too many formalities	14%
No Problem	24%

INTERPRETATION: According to the above graph and statistic, of the 130 respondents, 29% mentioned, 33% said it was time-consuming, 14% said there were too many formalities, and 24% said they had no issues with their favourite banks.

5. How much satisfied are you with your bank's overall performance?

Particulars	Percentage%
Excellent	72%
Very Good	14%
Good	14%

INTERPRETATION: Based on the aforementioned chart and figure, of the 130 respondents, 72% had excellent overall bank performance, 14% had very good overall bank performance, and 14% had fair overall bank performance.

FINDINGS

1. Higher percentage of person's bank accounts in public sector institutions.
2. The majority of defendants, including private and public sector banks, have savings accounts at their respective banks.
3. The public wants employees in public sector banks to behave differently when they are around consumers.
4. There should be more understanding of the issue of trust in private sector banks and the amount of money that remains in these banks in this region of the nation.
5. The public sector banks in this region of the nation provide greater fulfilment to the populace. The trust element and the branch's location are the primary causes of their satisfaction.

According to the research above, it is evident that the public sector bank defendants selected the specific banks because of their positive branches, i.e. geographically as well as because of faith.

Public sector banks that operate under the RBI's financial inclusion strategy have more clients since they offer what is now known as "no frill accounts," or BSBDA's (Basic Saving Bank Deposit Accounts) it is evident from the aforementioned analysis that BANCASSURANCE does not now exist in this region of the nation. Only a small percentage of respondents said that they were aware of these services, which also include credit card facilities and mobile banking.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

1. A few survey participants expressed reluctance to divulge personal information.
2. Because the research was approved quickly, the sample size and other characteristics were chosen to ensure that the work was of a high standard within the allotted time.
3. Because some of the accused may not have been involved in giving accurate information, the information they provided may have been biased.

SUGGESTIONS

The financial sector and the general public both greatly benefit from the services provided by banks. The variety and money generated by banks, as well as the cost and security of public funds, are among the most important aspects of the services they provide. During the inquiry, a number of financial and non-financial difficulties were found. The concerns that have been highlighted include issues with depositors, borrowers, employees, and management. When needed, the difficulties are thoroughly explained.

The public sector banks should hire more officers in a suitable manner to help the understaffed and undervalued branches become consistently self-sufficient. The bank management ought to be free to let go of the underperforming staff members. The work that public sector bank personnel do should be tied to targets; that is, they should be assigned specific jobs or targets with a specified quantity.

CONCLUSION

Our research indicates that a greater number of Vapi residents have faith in public banks than private ones. The main causes behind are as follows: Due to its semi-urban location, Vapi has fewer private sector bank branches and a lower level of public trust in these institutions. However, because public sector banks operate under the RBI's financial inclusion strategy, they have the appropriate number of branches here compared to private sector banks.

Nevertheless, given that the country's banking sector is anticipated to expand significantly over the next several years, private sector banks will have to increase the number of their Vapi branches in order to attract as many patrons of the mentioned establishment as feasible. For PSU Bank to maintain its substantial customer base, it must adopt a more optimistic outlook, prioritise customer relationship management, and undergo staff change to deliver genuine devotion to its clients.

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